

CAA Netherlands/Flanders – Annual Chapter Meeting 2019

Leuven, October 28–29th, 2019

LOCATION

The venue will take place in the Erasmushuis in Leuven. The auditorium, Justus Lipsiuszaal (LETT 08.16), is located on the 8th floor.

Address:

Erasmushuis
Blijde Inkomststraat 21
3000 Leuven
Belgium

MEETING PROGRAMME – OCTOBER 29TH

08:30 Registration

09:00 Welcome and introduction

09:10 Gary Lock: Unfolding vistas: moving, seeing and spatial thinking in archaeological GIS.

10:10 Stef Boogers: XylArch 2.0: a tool to estimate wood consumption in the past through Monte Carlo analysis in R.

10:35 Wouter Yperman: Extracting data and processing ASCII UTF-8 based file formats (aka plain text).

11:00 Coffee

11:15 Georgia Panagiotidou, Ralf Vandam, Andrew Vande Moere & Jeroen Poblome: Visualising Spatiotemporal Settlement Data for Pattern Discovery.

11:40 Dries Daems: Modelling the origin of *polis* in Anatolia. From conceptual to computational approaches.

12:05 Amanda Sengeløv, Giacomo Capuzzo, Sarah Dalle, Rica Annaert, Mathieu Boudin, Guy De Mulder, Marta Hlad, Ioannis Kontopoulos, Charlotte Sabaux, Kevin Salesse, Elisavet Stamataki, Dries Tys, Martine Vercauteren, Barbara Veselka, Eugène Warmenbol & Christophe Snoeck: Cremations, ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr and ¹⁴C: computational approaches to analyse past human mobility in Belgium.

12:30 Lunch¹

13:45 Roberto De Lima Hernandez, Harco Willems, Toon Sykora, Marleen De Meyer & Maarten Vergauwen: Documenting Djehutihotep's tomb at Dayr al-Barsha: Digital documentation and 3D reconstruction.

14:10 Adeline Hoffelinck: Spatial Analysis of a Roman Type of Market Building: Space Syntax as a Tool.

14:35 Ferry van den Oever & Nancy de Jong-Lambregts: Cold case: Kasteel De Middelburg (Alkmaar, NL).

15:00 Manuela Ritondale: Shipwrecks' location and coastal attractiveness: a predictive model for Mediterranean territorial waters.

15:25 Coffee

15:40 Danai Kafetzaki, Jeroen Poblome, Andrew Vande Moere & Jan Aerts: Deconstructing the collective reasoning of typology building by means of data and visual analytics.

16:05 Krijn Boom: Teaching through Play: Using video games as a platform to teach about the past.

16:30 Mark Gillings: Spatial Database as Assemblage? Exploring new theoretical frameworks for GIS through the mapping of liminality and affect.

17:30 Closing Drinks (at a nearby pub)

¹ Lunch is not provided by the organisation. There are several options for lunch near the venue.